

Synthesis of Pyrimidine Schiff bases as Potential Anticancer Agents*

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Manuscript received 16 October 1972; accepted 30 December 1972

Synthesis of seven pyrimidine Schiff bases are described as potential anticancer agents.

DURING the past two decades, many variations in the design of compounds on the theme of structure-activity studies have led to the synthesis and testing of thousands of potential anticancer compounds. Among various attempts to prepare compounds with greater specificity of action, the concept of "latent activity" has attracted a number of investigators. A series of practically inert azo compounds containing the nitrogen mustard moiety were synthesised¹ with the hope that these compounds might become activated by *in vivo* reduction of azo linkage by enzymes and several compounds in this series were found active against Walker rat carcinoma 256. As an extension of this approach a large number of Schiff bases, considered as isosteres of the azo mustards, were prepared²⁻⁴, some of which showed significant activity against Dunning leukemia in rats and a few compounds were considered promising for clinical trials^{5,6}. In this direction Modi, Sabnis and Deliwala⁷ have recently explored the field by preparing and testing a variety of Schiff base mustards many of which have shown interesting activity against experimental tumour systems. Further, some Schiff bases⁸ without having the alkylating nitrogen mustard moiety were synthesized and 4-*n*-hexyl-6-(2-hydroxy-phenyliminoethyl) resorcinol was found most active against Ehrlich ascites carcinoma, Sarcoma-180 and Yoshida sarcoma and it has been suggested that the azomethine linkage might be a structural requirement for the activity.

All these observations and the essential role of azomethine linkage in certain biological reactions⁹ have prompted us to synthesize some Schiff bases containing a nucleic acid component. This paper describes the synthesis of seven pyrimidine Schiff bases. Since Schiff bases are a class of compounds that hydrolyse readily under mild acidic conditions, such compounds could be hydrolysed selectively by the tumour cells as it is known that majority of the tumours contain cells with lower pH than cells in normal tissue¹⁰. Hydrolysis of these compounds *in vivo* may liberate the active aldehyde to act as alkylating agent and at the same time the pyrimidine

is freed to act as an antimetabolite. Besides, the azomethine linkage may be operative by a postulated chelation mechanism.

5-Amino uracil was selected as the starting material which was obtained by reduction of 5-nitrouracil by the method of Johnson and Matsuo¹². The preparation of the pyrimidine Schiff bases involved the condensation of 5-aminouracil with different substituted aromatic aldehydes. The condensation was accomplished by heating the former with appropriate aldehyde in aqueous ethanol for a definite length of time. The pyrimidine Schiff bases, deposited as crystalline solid on cooling, were collected on filter and recrystallized from ethanol. The following compounds were prepared: 5-(Benzylideneamino) uracil (I); 5-(2'-Hydroxy benzylideneamino) uracil (II); 5-(2'-chlorobenzylideneamino) uracil (III); 5-(3'-Nitro benzylideneamino) uracil (IV); 5-(4'-chlorobenzylideneamino) uracil (V); 5-(2'-Hydroxy-5'-bromobenzylideneamino) uracil (VI); 5-(4'-Methoxy benzylideneamino) uracil (VII). The constitution of these compounds were confirmed by their elemental analysis and ultraviolet absorption spectra. The usual pyrimidine absorption peak around 260 nm has been shifted to higher wave length i.e., 290-300 nm in these compounds. This can possibly be explained due to extended conjugation existing with the aromatic nucleus.

Experimental

The melting points were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. The ultraviolet spectra were measured in ethanol solution with a Hilger's spectrophotometer. The samples were dried *in vacuo* over phosphorus pentoxide at 80° for microanalysis. The analyses were carried out by Alfred Bernhardt of Max-Planck Institute, 433 Mühlheim, West Germany. The aromatic aldehydes were either freshly distilled or prepared before use. The experimental procedure being similar the preparation of 5-(Benzylideneamino) uracil is described here as a representative case.

5-(Benzylideneamino) uracil: 5-Amino uracil (0.76 g., 6 m moles) was dissolved in 60 ml. of hot distilled water. To this solution was added cautiously 0.64 g. (6 m moles) of freshly distilled benzaldehyde

* Presented at the IV National Cancer Conference held at Bangalore, Nov., 3-6, 1971.

TABLE 1

Compound	M.P.	Yield %	Formula	Analytical						UV Absorption spectra max in m μ
				Calculated%			Found %			
				C	H	N	C	H	N	
I. R ₁ , R ₂ , R ₃ , R ₄ = H	319-20°	98	C ₁₁ H ₉ O ₂ N ₃	61.93	4.22	19.52	60.91	4.05	19.82	290
II. R ₁ = OH; R ₂ , R ₃ , R ₄ = H	350-56°	90	C ₁₁ H ₉ O ₃ N ₃	57.14	3.92	18.17	56.96	3.71	18.01	300
III. R ₁ = Cl; R ₂ , R ₃ , R ₄ = H	318-20°	93	C ₁₁ H ₈ O ₂ N ₃ Cl	52.96	3.23	16.80	52.78	3.40	16.45	300
IV. R ₂ = NO ₂ ; R ₁ , R ₃ , R ₄ = H	322-23°	88	C ₁₁ H ₈ O ₄ N ₄	50.78	3.10	21.53	50.71	3.21	—	285
V. R ₃ = Cl; R ₁ , R ₂ , R ₄ = H	312-15°	87	C ₁₁ H ₈ O ₂ N ₃ Cl	52.96	3.23	16.80	52.69	3.03	16.52	300
VI. R ₁ = OH; R ₄ = Br; R ₂ , R ₃ = H	335-42°	90	C ₁₁ H ₈ O ₃ N ₃ Br	42.60	2.40	13.55	42.63	2.60	13.70	298
VII. R ₁ = OCH ₃ ; R ₂ , R ₃ , R ₄ = H	309-12°	84	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ O ₃ N ₃	58.77	4.52	17.13	58.57	4.35	16.92	297, 323

in 20 ml. of ethanol and the mixture was heated under reflux for 4 hr. at 120°-25° on a sand bath and left at room temperature overnight. The crystalline solid deposited was filtered, washed with hot water, and alcohol. M.p. 315°-18°, yield, 1.02 g. (98%). A portion of this product was repeatedly crystallized from ethanol to give the analytically pure-5(benzylideneamino) uracil, m.p. 319°-20°.

The physical characteristics of the different compounds prepared are given in Table 1.

Acknowledgements

The authors wish to express their sincere thanks to Col. N. Chatterjee, Director of this Centre for encouragement and interest in this work. The laboratory assistance offered by Shri Hari Das is thankfully acknowledged.

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